

PROCEDIN

Building Procurement Capability for Embedding and Driving Innovation

D2.2

Stakeholder Engagement Plan

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
EC	European Commission
EoI	Calls for Expression of Interest
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPTF	Innovation Procurement Task Force
POI	Procurement of Innovation
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovation
SEP	Stakeholder Engagement Plan
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
UA IRPP	URBAN AGENDA Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement
WP/T/D	Work Package/Task/Deliverable

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan

The purpose of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan (SEP) is to outline a strategic and systematic approach for effectively engaging with all relevant stakeholders throughout the PROCEDIN project. The plan serves as a comprehensive roadmap that guides the project team in understanding, involving, and communicating with various stakeholders, including individuals, organisations, institutions, and communities who have an interest or potential impact on the project's objectives and outcomes, especially related to expressing their interest to utilise project's services and results.

Furthermore, the Stakeholder Engagement Plan aims to foster productive and collaborative relationships with stakeholders, ensuring their active involvement and meaningful contributions throughout the project's lifecycle.

1.2 Scope and Objectives

D2.2. targets three principal project objectives, namely **Objective 2: to map and mobilise key POI stakeholders to accelerate and embed POI adoption**; **Objective 4: to facilitate procurement leadership in driving and embedding POI to generate dynamic innovation ecosystems**; and **Objective 5: to disseminate project activities, resources and other outcomes throughout the duration of the project, via multiple channels to reach all stakeholder groups**. Based on these three project objectives, the key objectives of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan include:

- **Building Trust and Transparency:** The plan aims to establish trust and transparency between the project team and stakeholders by openly sharing information, objectives, and progress updates. Transparent communication fosters confidence and promotes a positive project perception among stakeholders.
- **Identifying and Prioritising Stakeholders:** Through stakeholder analysis and mapping (D2.1), the plan identifies all relevant stakeholders and prioritises them based on their level of influence, interest, and potential impact on the project. This ensures that efforts are focused on engaging key stakeholders most effectively.
- **Tailoring Engagement Strategies:** The plan outlines tailored engagement strategies and activities for each stakeholder group. Different stakeholders may have distinct needs, expectations, and preferences, and the plan ensures that engagement efforts are customised to address these differences.
- **Encouraging Stakeholder Participation:** The plan seeks to actively involve stakeholders in various project activities, such as workshops, surveys, working groups, but engage them via calls for expressions of interest. By providing opportunities for meaningful participation, stakeholders become co-creators of project solutions and feel valued in the decision-making process.

Effective management of **stakeholder expectations** is essential for the project's success, and this involves maintaining transparent communication and sustaining consistent engagement to keep stakeholders informed about project progress, potential challenges, and anticipated outcomes.

Furthermore, engaging stakeholders will provide to PROCEDIN a valuable source of diverse perspectives and expertise that enriches project strategies. Incorporating their feedback and insights ensures **the project remains contextually relevant and significantly enhances its impact**. The SEP is intentionally designed to be dynamic, capable of adapting to evolving stakeholder needs and shifting project circumstances. Regular reviews and updates will guarantee the continued relevance and effectiveness of engagement strategies throughout the project's lifecycle.

1.3 GDPR Compliance, Ethical Requirements, and Data Protection

Within the domain of stakeholder engagement, the PROCEDIN project maintains a resolute dedication to ethical standards, GDPR compliance, and the implementation of robust data protection measures. These principles serve as the bedrock of project's engagement strategy, shaping our interactions with stakeholders. More information can be found in PROCEDIN's D6.2 Data Management Plan.

PROCEDIN fully adheres to the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** principles. This means that the personal data of stakeholders, such as contact information or other identifying details, is collected, processed, and stored with strict adherence to GDPR guidelines. The Project's commitment to GDPR compliance ensures the privacy and data protection rights of stakeholders are preserved at all times.

Prior to engaging with stakeholders (e.g., while running Calls for Expressions of Interest), PROCEDIN will seek **informed consent** for data collection and processing. PROCEDIN is transparent about how stakeholder data will be used, ensuring they understand and agree to its purposes. Additionally, stakeholders have the right to withdraw their consent at any time, granting them control over their personal data.

In line with project's commitment to responsible data management, consortium partners also adhere to a **Data Minimisation** approach, only collecting information that is pivotal for effective engagement. Unnecessary data is neither collected nor retained, thereby mitigating privacy risks and ensuring that the information the project possesses remains highly relevant to its engagement objectives.

PROCEDIN engages with stakeholders with the utmost respect for **ethical considerations**. All interactions are conducted in a fair, transparent, and respectful manner, ensuring that stakeholder autonomy and rights are upheld.

Lastly, by establishing clear **Data Retention and Deletion** policies, stakeholder data is retained only for as long as necessary to achieve the objectives of the engagement. After this period, data is securely deleted to protect stakeholder privacy.

2 Stakeholder Analysis

2.1 Stakeholder Identification

Within the PROCEDIN project there is a particular focus on procurement of innovation in the context of innovation in European cities' to address their sustainability and resilience agendas.

The segmentation of stakeholders into four distinct clusters (Table 1), as detailed in **D2.1 Accessible map of ecosystems, reporting on clusters' needs, capabilities, and barriers to procurement of innovation**, is a strategic approach to categorise and better understand the diverse actors within the POI landscape.

Each cluster represents a specific role or function within this complex ecosystem, and this segmentation approach enhances the project's ability to tailor engagement strategies and communication efforts to the specific needs and interests of each stakeholder cluster.

Table 1. *PROCEDIN Stakeholder Identification*

Innovation Demand (Innovation Buyers):
<p>Definition: This cluster comprises organisations or individuals, whether from the public or private sector, who have identified a need or desire for innovative products, services, or solutions to address particular challenges or meet specific requirements.</p> <p>Role: They act as the driving force behind the procurement of innovation, initiating the process by expressing their demand for novel solutions.</p> <p>Importance: Understanding the requirements and preferences of innovation demand stakeholders is critical for aligning innovation supply with market needs.</p>
Innovation Supply (Innovation Providers):
<p>Definition: This cluster encompasses a diverse range of entities, including SMEs, startups, spin-offs, universities, incubators, and technology centers. They are instrumental in the creation, development, and delivery of innovative products, services, or solutions.</p> <p>Role: Innovation suppliers play a pivotal role in bringing inventive concepts to fruition, contributing to research, development, and commercialization.</p> <p>Importance: Recognising the capabilities and contributions of innovation supply stakeholders is essential for fostering collaborations and ensuring a seamless flow of innovative solutions to meet demand.</p>
Multipliers (Enablers and Facilitators):
<p>Definition: This category includes a wide array of stakeholders, such as intermediaries, advocacy groups, associations, consultants, and policy formulators, collectively referred to as "multipliers." They serve as intermediaries or enablers, facilitating and strengthening innovation-related activities.</p> <p>Role: Multipliers play a bridging role, connecting innovation suppliers with innovation demanders and providing various forms of support and expertise.</p> <p>Importance: Their involvement is instrumental in overcoming barriers, promoting best practices, and creating an enabling environment for innovation in procurement.</p>
Projects (Initiatives linked to Innovation Procurement):
<p>Definition: This cluster is dedicated to specific initiatives, ventures, or projects that revolve around innovation procurement practices. Activities within this category encompass strategic formulation, market analysis, specification development, procurement process management, training, and impact evaluation related to procurement of innovation.</p> <p>Role: Projects in this cluster are at the forefront of advancing POI practices, contributing to the development of methodologies, tools, and best practices.</p> <p>Importance: These initiatives serve as exemplars and knowledge hubs, disseminating valuable insights and driving the adoption of POI approaches.</p>

2.2 Stakeholder Mapping

Since this task relies on work carried out by T2.1, the initial engagement will start with stakeholders found in the scouting and mapping activity. These stakeholders are visually represented via an interactive map¹ (Figure 1; contact details concealed for confidentiality), accessible on the PROCEDIN website. This map offers a user-friendly approach to exploring Public Procurement of Innovation (POI) stakeholders throughout Europe by means of visual and geographical assessment. Users can efficiently pinpoint the concentration of stakeholders within a specific geographical area of interest, apply filters based on stakeholder categories, and gain insights into their primary services via concise descriptions.

Figure 1. Interactive Map of POI Stakeholders

Each stakeholder entity is conveniently linked to its respective website. It's important to note that the interactive map will remain dynamic and continuously updated by F6S, extending beyond the conclusion of the PROCEDIN project. This strategic decision, supported by the five-year availability of the project website's domain, is aimed at fostering sustained engagement, increased traffic, and the continued utilisation of PROCEDIN's valuable resources. It stands as a lasting reference point for POI stakeholders, welcoming resource suggestions from both project partners and website users through the dedicated website section.

2.3 Stakeholder Interests

Within the PROCEDIN project there is a special focus on procurement of innovation in the context of the circular economy and greening mobility, whilst recognising the multi-faceted and complex innovation needs of European cities' sustainability and resilience agendas.

Stakeholder interests within the context of PROCEDIN are multifaceted, reflecting the diverse goals, stakes, and potential benefits of embracing a circular economy paradigm, and greening mobility. For many stakeholders, including innovative businesses and suppliers, the circular economy offers a **promising avenue for sustainable growth and competitiveness**. Their interests lie in accessing new markets, reducing resource dependencies, and achieving long-term economic stability. Public sector

¹ <https://procedin.eu/stakeholder-map/>

stakeholders, on the other hand, often seek to **enhance sustainability**, reduce environmental impact, and create resilient, future-ready communities. Their interests are aligned with the circular economy's potential to address waste reduction, resource efficiency, and POI practices.

In terms of expectations, stakeholders anticipate that PROCEDIN will **provide actionable insights, best practices, and concrete strategies** for procurement of innovation to implement circular economy principles. They look to the project to offer guidance on policy formulation, market development, and sustainable practices. These expectations are anchored in the belief that the project will deliver valuable knowledge and tools for driving the circular economy agenda forward.

Concurrent with their expectations, stakeholders harbor concerns and risks. They may worry about the **costs and complexities of transitioning to circular economy models** or the potential disruptions to existing business practices. Additionally, stakeholders may have needs, such as access to training, resources, or POI support to facilitate their circular economy efforts.

Conversely, the project seeks active engagement and collaboration from stakeholders to **co-create solutions and disseminate best practices**. PROCEDIN seeks the commitment of stakeholders to participate in knowledge exchange, pilot projects, and policy advocacy, all of which are vital to achieving the circular economy's transformative potential.

3 Engagement Goals and Strategies

The overall engagement goals of the PROCEDIN project are rooted in a commitment to effective stakeholder involvement and collaboration. By aligning the project's objectives with the unique needs and aspirations of stakeholders within each cluster—Innovation Demand, Innovation Supply, Multipliers, and Projects—the project aspires to achieve several key outcomes.

Firstly, it aims to foster a culture of open dialogue and knowledge exchange, nurturing a comprehensive understanding of procurement of innovation practices. Secondly, the project endeavours to create networking opportunities that enhance existing communities of practice and learning while also reaching new stakeholder groups and individuals within established clusters.

Finally, by connecting with citizen and civil society groups through the common thread of the POI domain, the project seeks to promote greater inclusivity in governance models and more meaningful engagement in policymaking.

3.1 Specific Engagement Objectives

In pursuit of successful stakeholder engagement, the PROCEDIN project has crafted tailored objectives for each stakeholder group, each designed to address the distinct roles and requirements of these vital contributors.

For **Innovation Buyers**, the objective is **to engage closely** with these stakeholders to truly understand their requirements, challenges, and goals when it comes to procurement of innovation. The project aims to educate them about the benefits of POI through webinars and workshops, facilitate connections with potential innovation suppliers, and provide resources to support local POI capacity building. Importantly, partners are committed to keeping an open feedback loop to ensure that the consortium is always responsive to their evolving needs.

For **Innovation Supply**, the project provides a platform for these stakeholders to showcase their ground-breaking products and services, demonstrating their capabilities to potential buyers.

Moreover, PROCEDIN also offers **capacity-building opportunities** through workshops and training sessions, helping them navigate the procurement process effectively. The networking events and workshops are designed to foster collaboration and connections among innovation supply stakeholders, and the partners will keep stakeholders informed about emerging market trends and demand, helping them tailor their innovations to evolving needs.

Multipliers, in their role as enablers and facilitators, are invited to engage in **knowledge sharing**, participate in policy dialogues, explore partnership opportunities, collaborate for capacity building, and bridge connections between various stakeholder groups. Lastly, **Projects** linked to Procurement of Innovation are tasked with **showcasing their impact**, sharing knowledge, encouraging the adoption of POI practices, and forging collaboration opportunities with fellow initiatives. These tailored objectives are rooted in the human-centred principle of understanding and meeting the unique needs and aspirations of each stakeholder group.

3.2 Stakeholder Engagement Considerations

In the context of PROCEDIN's Stakeholder Engagement Considerations, there are a multitude of factors that demand careful consideration from all clusters of stakeholders. Engaging stakeholders carries both costs and benefits for all parties involved:

1. **Time and Resource Investment:** Establishing relationships built on trust is a time-intensive and resource-demanding endeavour. To ensure comprehensive stakeholder engagement while effectively managing limited time and resources, PROCEDIN will meticulously outline the engagement process in advance, especially related to Expressions of Interest. This strategic approach will enable project partners to engage with a broad spectrum of relevant stakeholders, leaving no willing participant excluded.
2. **Managing Expectations:** Stakeholder engagement can inadvertently foster unrealistically high expectations among participants regarding the impact of their involvement in the project or the project's influence on specific policy outcomes. To preempt potential dissatisfaction, PROCEDIN will provide clear and transparent explanations to stakeholders about their expected roles throughout the project.
3. **Managing Consultation Fatigue:** Stakeholders often experience fatigue with prolonged engagement processes, particularly when results are not immediately evident. PROCEDIN will proactively address this issue by ensuring that stakeholders are well-informed about the benefits of expressing their interest to join, processes and the project timeline. Additionally, PROCEDIN will maintain a continuous dialogue with stakeholders through regular communication cycles to keep them engaged and informed throughout the project's duration.

3.3 Stakeholder Engagement Levels

On a geographical level, PROCEDIN aims to foster collaboration across regional, cross-regional, and European levels. When determining the frequency and selecting suitable engagement techniques for specific stakeholder groups within PROCEDIN, four pivotal criteria come into play:

1. **Interest Level:** The degree of interest a particular stakeholder group has in actively participating in the project serves as a fundamental criterion. Highly engaged groups, with a vested interest in project outcomes, may warrant more frequent and intensive engagement

efforts. Conversely, groups with lower interest levels may benefit from less frequent but equally meaningful interactions.

2. **Influence Potential:** The extent to which a stakeholder group holds influence over the project's direction and decisions is another crucial factor. Groups with significant influence should be engaged more frequently and extensively to ensure their perspectives shape the project effectively. For less influential groups, engagement efforts can be tailored to align with their level of impact.
3. **Appropriate Engagement Methods:** The selection of engagement and knowledge elicitation methods should align with the preferences and characteristics of each stakeholder group. Some groups may prefer direct meetings and workshops, while others may be more receptive to online forums or surveys. The chosen methods should resonate with the specific group's communication style and facilitate effective knowledge exchange.
4. **Knowledge Actors:** From the project's outset, PROCEDIN has actively engaged key Quadruple Helix knowledge actors in its stakeholder activities. This approach involves academia, industry, government, and civil society.

Considering these four criteria, PROCEDIN ensures that its stakeholder engagement efforts are not only efficient but also tailored to the unique needs and attributes of each group, fostering a more meaningful and productive engagement process.

4 Engagement Activities & Expression of Interest

4.1 Stakeholder Engagement Matrix

The following **Stakeholder Engagement Matrix** (Table 2) outlines the key stakeholder clusters, their roles, and the corresponding engagement strategies and activities. The engagement strategies and activities outlined in the matrix are indicative and may evolve throughout the project to align with stakeholder feedback and changing project dynamics. The goal is to create a dynamic and inclusive engagement environment that enhances stakeholder collaboration and supports the project's objectives.

Table 2. Stakeholder Engagement Matrix

Stakeholder Cluster	Role/Type	Engagement Strategy	Engagement Activities
Innovation Demand	(Public) Entities seeking innovative solutions and products.	Understand their specific needs and challenges. Showcase how POI can address needs. Facilitate connections with innovation supply stakeholders. Share resources for local capacity building.	Surveys and interviews to gather requirements and preferences. Webinars and workshops on the benefits of POI. Matchmaking events and community platforms to connect with relevant stakeholders.

<p>Innovation Supply</p>	<p>SMEs, start-ups, universities, and technology centres.</p>	<p>Highlight their capabilities and innovations.</p> <p>Provide support for capacity building and collaboration.</p> <p>Encourage collaboration and networking.</p>	<p>Innovation showcases and exhibitions.</p> <p>Workshops on accessing procurement opportunities.</p> <p>Networking events and industry-specific forums.</p>
<p>Multipliers</p>	<p>Intermediaries, consultants, advocacy groups, associations, educators.</p> <p>Policy formulators, enablers of POI.</p>	<p>Facilitate knowledge exchange and best practices.</p> <p>Support the development of an enabling environment.</p> <p>Bridge connections between demanders and suppliers.</p> <p>Promote new approaches to capacity building.</p>	<p>Expert panel discussions and knowledge-sharing sessions.</p> <p>Policy dialogues and workshops on POI regulations and capacity building.</p> <p>Partnership opportunities with multipliers.</p>
<p>Projects</p>	<p>Initiatives focused on POI practices.</p> <p>Knowledge hubs and exemplars for POI.</p>	<p>Close collaboration and cross-fertilisation of project outcomes and lessons learned.</p> <p>Disseminate valuable knowledge, and promote capacity building.</p> <p>Advocate the adoption of POI methodologies and approaches.</p>	<p>Project showcases and impact evaluation presentations.</p> <p>Webinars and seminars on POI methodologies.</p> <p>Collaboration opportunities between project initiatives.</p>

4.2 Calls for Expression of Interest

The promotion and launch of an **Expression of Interest** (EoI) for potential beneficiaries of the PROCEDIN project is a critical initiative. This task not only seeks to engage potential beneficiaries but also aims to foster connections and networks between buyers and suppliers in the field of Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI).

Besides attracting potential beneficiaries, the EoI also aims to facilitate connections between buyers and suppliers, support the establishment of new partnerships and consortia among suppliers, and facilitate new connections between stakeholders across the innovation ecosystem for POI policy dialogue and collaborative capacity building.

The timeline and action plan proposed (Table 3) will guide the effective promotion and launch of the EoI, and envisages the **timeframe** between the submission of this plan (**M13**) and the project’s final event (**M21**), as well as the timeframe after the final event and the project end date (M24).

Table 3. Expression of Interest Timeline and Action Points

Phase	Duration	Action Points
Preparation Phase	Months 13–14 <i>(November and December 2023)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify and segment potential beneficiaries into categories (buyers, suppliers, consortia, etc.). Develop a clear and compelling EoI document outlining the objectives, benefits, and expectations. Set up a dedicated EoI section on the PROCEDIN project website, and prepare the Registration Form. Draft communication materials, including emails, social media posts, and website content. Define the evaluation criteria and process for EoI responses.
Promotion Phase	Months 15–17 <i>(January, February, and March 2024)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launch the EoI and disseminate it through multiple channels, including the project website, social media, newsletters, and partner networks. Collaborate with the Urban Agenda partnership for innovative and responsible public procurement, the TENDERIO platform and IPTF to reach a wider audience. Engage in direct outreach to potential beneficiaries, including buyers and suppliers, through targeted emails and industry-specific forums. Maintain an active presence on relevant industry platforms and forums to attract attention to the EoI.
Engagement and Evaluation Phase	Month 18 <i>(April 2024)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Begin the evaluation of EoI responses, considering criteria such as relevance, potential impact, and alignment with project objectives. Facilitate dialogue with respondents, seeking additional information or clarification where necessary. Identify and notify beneficiaries who expressed their interest to actively participate in the project. Engage selected beneficiaries in onboarding and orientation activities to ensure a smooth transition into the project.
Networking and Partnership Phase	Months 19–21 <i>(May and June 2024)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organise networking events, virtual or in-person, to bring together selected beneficiaries, encouraging connections and knowledge exchange. Facilitate discussions and matchmaking sessions between buyers and suppliers, with a dedicated session during the Final Event (M21). Encourage the formation of consortia and partnerships among suppliers interested in collaborative PPI efforts. Explore synergy opportunities with other relevant initiatives to amplify networking and partnership outcomes.
Ongoing Support and Monitoring	Months 22–24 <i>(July 2024 until the end of the project)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuously monitor and support the active participation of beneficiaries in the project. Evaluate the impact of new partnerships and consortia on knowledge exchange and joint PPI participation. Provide ongoing assistance, resources, and guidance to beneficiaries to ensure their successful engagement. Planning for continuation, and collect feedback to improve the EoI process for possible future rounds and adapt the engagement strategy as needed.

4.2.1 Support and Capacity-Building Activities

The support and capacity-building activities (Table 4) associated with the EoI in the PROCEDIN project are designed to not only attract potential beneficiaries but also to empower and enable them to actively engage in the project. The activities will be organised over the course of the EoI process to ensure a smooth and supportive experience for all participants.

Table 4. Expression of Interest: Supporting and Capacity-Building Activities

Phase	Duration	Activity Description
Pre-EoI Engagement	Months 13–14 <i>(November and December 2023)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Information Workshops: PROCEDIN will organise informative online workshops, and utilise in-person events, to introduce potential beneficiaries to the PROCEDIN project, its goals, and the EoI process. These workshops will explain the benefits of participation and provide clarity on expectations. ▪ Promote the Resource Bank: Partners will disseminate the PROCEDIN Resource Bank, which offers guides, templates, and best practice examples related to POI and PPI. The Resource Bank is accessible to all stakeholders via project’s website to support their understanding and involvement in the EoI.
EoI Launch and Promotion	Months 15–17 <i>(January, February, and March 2024)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Webinars: Partners will conduct webinars on the EoI’s objectives, the application process, and the potential benefits of participation. These webinars will be open to all stakeholders, enhancing transparency and promoting inclusivity. ▪ PROCEDIN Community: Consortium will establish a community forum/page/group (either on the F6S Platform or via LinkedIn) to offer guidance sessions for potential beneficiaries. These sessions will provide tailored assistance to address specific questions or concerns, fostering a sense of inclusiveness and support.
EoI Response and Selection	Month 18 <i>(April 2024)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Application Clinics: Partners will keep utilising the PROCEDIN Community and workshops to host “clinics” to guide applicants through the process of submitting EoI responses. These clinics can be both virtual and in-person, offering hands-on support in completing applications. ▪ Selection Feedback: Consortium will provide feedback to all EoI applicants, regardless of selection. This feedback will help unsuccessful entities to understand areas for.
Ongoing Engagement and Support	Months 19–24 <i>(May 2024 and until the end of the project)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Matchmaking Programme: Partners will establish a matchmaking programme that pairs new members, particularly from citizen and civil society groups, with experienced innovation buyers/suppliers within the community. This programme will promote learning and knowledge transfer. ▪ Access to Knowledge Base and Guidance: PROCEDIN will maintain a comprehensive knowledge base (Resource Bank) on

		the project website, regularly updated with resources and news related to POI. Moreover, partners will offer ongoing guidance to all beneficiaries, assisting them in navigating the project's various phases and activities.
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4.3 Communication Channel, Events and Platforms

PROCEDIN employs a variety of communication tools and channels, spanning online, offline, and face-to-face interactions, facilitated by partners to ensure effective engagement with diverse stakeholders. These resources cater to both general and specific target groups. Leveraging the expertise and diverse interactions of PROCEDIN partners with their audiences, the project emphasises unique communication channels already proven successful in day-to-day interactions.

4.3.1 Project Website

PROCEDIN's website² stands as a central platform for public engagement, meticulously tailored to cater to a diverse array of project audiences. It offers users a seamless navigation experience, allowing them to access continuously updated, crucial project information that pertains to their specific interests.

Managed by F6S and collaboratively contributed to by all project partners, this website serves as an indispensable management tool, streamlining the dissemination and communication of project activities and outcomes across various stakeholder levels. It provides valuable insights into project objectives, solutions, scope, partners, and expectations.

Furthermore, the website will serve as the **primary source of information for EoI**, offering stakeholders a **one-stop destination** for all the necessary information they require.

4.3.2 Project and Third-Party Events

Leveraging both project-specific and third-party events provides valuable opportunities to connect, share knowledge, and foster collaboration with stakeholders.

Speaking of project-specific events, organising **webinars** within the project framework offers stakeholders a platform for in-depth discussions. Such events enable the sharing of knowledge, project updates, and interactive engagement, ensuring stakeholders stay informed and connected. Furthermore, regular **collaborative workshops** will facilitate direct interactions between the PROCEDIN team and engaged stakeholders, as it is envisaged for these engagements to foster rapport, clarify project objectives, and encourage active participation. PROCEDIN will leverage its **Final Event** as an in-person networking opportunity and to attract a diverse group of stakeholders. The Final Event will offer a comprehensive view of the project's achievements, encourages networking, and showcases innovative practices in procurement.

When it comes to **third-party events**, PROCEDIN will utilise its participation at **conferences** related to innovation, sustainability, or public procurement to engage with stakeholders from diverse backgrounds. The team will aim to present project updates and success stories, during such events to gain awareness and attract new stakeholders. Furthermore, partners will aim to host **dedicated panels or sessions** within larger conferences that can position PROCEDIN as an expert in the field, as such

² procedin.eu

sessions allow for knowledge sharing and networking, while also aligning with the goals of the project. Consortium will also explore the opportunity of setting up **booths or exhibitions** at relevant third-party events that provide visibility and opportunities for face-to-face interactions. During these in person occasions, PROCEDIN is planning to employ the "live-posting" method across social media (specifically X) to emphasise and distribute the crucial insights and pertinent messages arising from the discussions. A tentative list of third-party events where PROCEDIN envisages its participation can be found within Table 5.

Table 5. Provisional List of Third-Party Events

Event Name	Date and Location	Description
Smart City Expo World Congress	November 7-9, 2023 Barcelona, Spain	Smart City Expo World Congress is the world's biggest and most influential event on urban innovation. The event connects leaders from the most innovative companies, governments and organisations to move cities towards a better future.
Innovation Roundtable Summit	November 7-9, 2023 Copenhagen, Denmark	The Summit is open exclusively to innovation professionals in large multinational companies – the world's largest gathering of its kind – providing a unique setting for in-depth dialogue and valuable networking among corporate peers.
International Conference on Smart Cities and Sustainable Solutions	January 14-15, 2024 Zurich, Switzerland	International Conference on Smart Cities and Sustainable Solutions aims to bring together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and research results on all aspects of Smart Cities and Sustainable Solutions.
International Conference on Smart Cities and Sustainable Development	February 8-9, 2024 Lisbon, Portugal	International Conference on Smart Cities and Sustainable Development aims to bring together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and research results on all aspects of Smart Cities and Sustainable Development.
PSI: Procurement Strategies & Innovation	March 5, 2024 London, United Kingdom	PSI 2024 is a uniquely vibrant showcase of everything that's new in the procurement profession. PSI will focus on bringing together a group of senior practitioners, innovators and creative thinkers, and unite them in solving many of the industry's most common challenges.
11th Procura+ Conference	March 13-14, 2024 Lisbon, Portugal	Procura+ conference is where sustainable, circular and innovation procurement policy meets practice, and where procurement innovations have originated. The event gathers representatives of the EC, mayors of leading cities, business leaders, researchers and some of the brightest procurement minds.
URBAN AGENDA Partnership Meeting	April TBA, 2024	The UA Partnership's primary audience are cities, regions and member states. By creating a network with expert organisations, European Institutions,

	Haarlem, the Netherlands	SME's and stakeholders UA creates knowledge and information exchange to reach its goals.
Forum Compraverde Buygreen	May TBA, 2024 Rome, Italy	Forum Compraverde Buygreen is the reference event in Europe for public and private Green Procurement policies, projects, goods and services.
Urban Future 2024	June 5-7, 2024 Rotterdam, the Netherlands	The event's mission is to support changes in other cities for the better, by connecting with the world's most impressive urban change-makers. It is Europe's largest events for urban sustainability, taking place in different cities and virtually, and through its global community of more than 50,000 stakeholders and 200+ organisations.
EXPANDEO 2024	June 12-13, 2024 Brussels, Belgium	EXPANDEO is the event where the European Earth Observation companies alongside other stakeholders get the opportunity to learn through interactive sessions about current policies where the sector could make a contribution & various market opportunities while growing your business networking.
Procurement Summit	June 12-13, 2024 Hamburg, Germany	The Procurement Summit is the exhibition for digitalisation and innovation in the procurement sector, including top-class speakers, panel discussions among leading experts, workshops with applicable expertise such as innovative providers in the exhibition area.

4.3.3 PROCEDIN Channel Mix

In the context of PROCEDIN's Stakeholder Engagement Considerations, there are a multitude of factors that demand careful consideration from all clusters of stakeholders.

Leveraging project's **social media channels**, particularly **X** (formerly Twitter)³ and **LinkedIn**⁴, is an important component of PROCEDIN's strategy to engage stakeholders and encourage their Expression of Interest in the project. These platforms serve as dynamic spaces where project partners regularly communicate and disseminate pertinent content (see example: Figure 2), share success stories, and interact directly with its target stakeholders.

Partners will craft and promote **informative blogs** (more in 4.3.3.1), **engaging infographics**, **explainer videos**, and illuminating case studies, with the aim to both educate and inspire potential beneficiaries. Furthermore, the presentation of testimonials and success narratives from existing stakeholders and partners will serve as a persuasive form of social proof, fostering trust and motivating others to express their interest.

To enhance the reach of its **tailored messages** (more in 4.3.3.2), PROCEDIN will implement targeted advertising campaigns. These campaigns will underscore the unique advantages of joining PROCEDIN,

³ <https://twitter.com/procedin>

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/procedin/>

thereby augmenting the number of Eols. Additionally, partners will **host webinars** on subjects aligned with project's themes, and promote these events via social media channels and encouraging participation. Engaging in **conversations with stakeholders**, responding to their queries, and maintaining an **active online community** are also central to the PROCEDIN approach. Collaboration with thought leaders, industry experts, and stakeholders will further expand the social media presence, and have direct calls to submit Eols.

Figure 2. Social Media Announcement Example

4.3.3.1 Content Types

The overall purpose of PROCEDIN’s content marketing efforts will be to support the target audience’s journey towards decision making (i.e., apply to the Eol). In this regard, the following types of content (Table 6) will be developed:

Table 6. Content Types

Attract	Engage	Maintain	Galvanise
<p>Explainer videos, articles, infographics; thought leadership outreach</p>	<p>Blog posts, whitepapers, webinars, interviews, industry reports;</p>	<p>Email marketing, social ads, targeting initiatives;</p>	<p>Workshops, conferences, Final Event.</p>

Table 7 outlines a series of potential engaging articles and blog posts aimed at disseminating valuable insights, knowledge, and updates to our diverse stakeholders. Each theme serves to inform and engage stakeholders, showcasing the state-of-the-art practices in procurement of innovation, providing a comprehensive understanding of the PROCEDIN project, and emphasising the compelling benefits of active participation within the PROCEDIN network.

Table 7. Direction of Themes and Topics of Communication

Theme	Potential Article Topic
Procurement of Innovation State-of-the-Art	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The Evolution of Procurement of Innovation. ▪ Global Best Practices in Procurement of Innovation. ▪ The Role of SMEs in Driving Innovation. ▪ Innovative Practices in Sustainability and Responsible Procurement.
Understanding PROCEDIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Navigating the PROCEDIN Project: Enhancing Procurement of Innovation. ▪ Resource Bank: Your Gateway to Procurement of Innovation Knowledge. ▪ Connecting Stakeholders in PROCEDIN: A Network for Innovation.
Benefits of Joining PROCEDIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unlocking Opportunities: Why Joining PROCEDIN Matters. ▪ Accelerating Your Innovation Journey with PROCEDIN. ▪ From Knowledge to Action: How PROCEDIN Transforms Insights into Impact ▪ How PROCEDIN Can Impacted its Stakeholders?

4.3.3.2 Narrative and Messages

Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 6 provide an insightful and humanised perspective on the stakeholders, encapsulating their interests, needs, goals, and potential benefits concerning the innovation procurement.

While crafting these persona cards, PROCEDIN aims to create a more vivid and comprehensive image of the key players within each cluster, allowing partners to tailor the engagement strategy more effectively and cultivate more meaningful and productive relationships with its stakeholders.

Figure 3. Persona Card: Innovation Demand

PROCEDIN *Persona 2: Innovation Supply (Innovation Provider)*
Esteban Barbosa
 CEO and Founder

Background:
 Esteban is the CEO and founder of a startup known for developing cutting-edge technology solutions. He is passionate about bringing innovation to the market.

Goals and Pain Points:

- **Goal:** Esteban wants to expand his startup's reach by securing contracts with organisations looking for innovative solutions.
- **Pain Point:** He faces challenges in navigating the procurement processes and connecting with potential clients.

Engagement Strategy:

- Esteban is likely to participate in innovation showcases and exhibitions to demonstrate his products.
- Workshops that offer guidance on accessing procurement opportunities would be valuable to him.

Figure 4. Persona Card: Innovation Supply

PROCEDIN *Persona 3: Multipliers (Enablers and Facilitators)*
Margareth Company
 Managing Director

Background:
 Margareth leads a firm that assists businesses in bridging the gap between innovation and procurement. She is passionate about facilitating innovation adoption.

Goals and Pain Points:

- **Goal:** Margareth aims to facilitate knowledge exchange and best practices among her clients.
- **Pain Point:** She faces challenges in connecting her clients with suitable suppliers and procurement opportunities, and in sourcing suitable resources for developing POI knowledge and skills in client teams.

Engagement Strategy:

- Margareth is interested in expert panel discussions and knowledge-sharing sessions.
- She values partnership opportunities and policy dialogues related to innovative procurement.

Figure 5. Persona Card: Multipliers

PROCEDIN *Persona 4: Projects and Initiatives*
Xavier Arçenois
 Project Manager

Background:
 Xavier manages a project focused on promoting innovative procurement practices. He is dedicated to advancing procurement methodologies.

Goals and Pain Points:

- **Goal:** Xavier wants to promote project outcomes and encourage the adoption of innovative procurement approaches.
- **Pain Point:** He faces challenges in disseminating project knowledge effectively.

Engagement Strategy:

- Xavier values project showcases and impact evaluation presentations to share project achievements.
- He actively participates in webinars and seminars that discuss innovative procurement methodologies.

Figure 6. Persona Card: Projects and Initiatives

4.3.4 Supporting Initiatives, Partnerships and Platforms

PROCEDIN has a unique opportunity to leverage and collaborate with several impactful initiatives and platforms to enhance stakeholder engagement and achieve its overarching objectives. Through strategic alliances with the Tenderio Platform, UA IRPP, and the Innovation Procurement Task Force, PROCEDIN can foster a broader and more diverse network of stakeholders, facilitating meaningful connections and knowledge exchange.

Tenderio Platform⁵, with its pan-European consultancy network, can serve as a valuable resource to help SMEs and potential beneficiaries navigate the public procurement landscape efficiently. By partnering with Tenderio, which is run by PEDAL, PROCEDIN will connect stakeholders with expert consultancies and offer tailored support, enhancing their capacity to engage effectively.

The **URBAN AGENDA Partnership for Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement**⁶ provides a platform for aligning public procurement strategies with broader urban objectives, and it is coordinated by HAA. This way, PROCEDIN can engage with city authorities, expanding the project's reach and impact while aligning with the Partnership's goals.

The **Innovation Procurement Task Force**⁷ represents a collaborative hub for various EU-funded projects focusing on POI (e.g., BUILD, InnoFacilitator, InnoBuyer). PROCEDIN's involvement as a founding in this task force can offer stakeholders an array of opportunities for networking, learning, and sharing insights on innovation procurement. Joint activities and events can facilitate interaction among project participants, driving the collective advancement of innovation procurement practices.

5 Monitoring and Evaluation

5.1 Key Performance Indicators

The PROCEDIN project employs a set of **provisional KPIs** to assess the effectiveness of its stakeholder engagement strategies. These KPIs have been crafted to align with the project's objectives and provide insights into engagement outcomes. Following are three selected indicators that are elaborated in Table 8:

- Stakeholder Participation Rate
- Expression of Interest Response Rate
- Networking and Partnership Formation

These **suggested rates** serve as targets for the PROCEDIN project and should be monitored regularly to assess progress and effectiveness in stakeholder engagement efforts. It's important to adjust these rates as needed to align with the project's specific goals and evolving circumstances.

Table 8. Provisional Key Performance Indicators

KPI 1: Stakeholder Participation Rate

The Stakeholder Participation Rate can be calculated by dividing the number of actively engaged stakeholders by the total number of stakeholders within the PROCEDIN project.

⁵ <https://www.tenderio.com/>

⁶ <https://www.urbanagenda.urban-initiative.eu/partnerships/public-procurement>

⁷ <https://procedin.eu/innovation-procurement-task-force/>

Stakeholder Participation Rate

$$= \left(\frac{\text{Number of Actively Engaged Stakeholders}}{\text{Total Number of Engaged Stakeholders}} \right) \times 100$$

- **Number of Actively Engaged Stakeholders:** This represents the count of stakeholders who have been actively involved in project activities, events, surveys, or feedback loops. Active engagement could include attending project events, providing feedback, participating in workshops, and other forms of interaction with the project.
- **Total Number of Engaged Stakeholders:** This is the comprehensive count of all identified stakeholders within the PROCEDIN project that initially expressed their interest. It includes stakeholders from all clusters and categories.

Suggested KPI Rate: 70%. A 70% participation rate indicates a robust and engaged stakeholder community. This rate suggests that a majority of relevant stakeholders are actively involved in the project's activities and engagement efforts.

KPI 2: Call for Expression of Interest Response Rate

Call for Expression of Interest (Eol) Response Rate can be calculated by dividing the number of received Eols by the total number of Eols sent or promoted, and then multiplying the result by 100 to express it as a percentage.

$$\text{Eol Response Rate} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of Received Eols}}{\text{Total Number of Sent or Promoted Eols}} \right) \times 100$$

The Eol Response Rate provides insights into how effectively the call for Eols has engaged potential beneficiaries and motivated them to express their interest in the PROCEDIN project.

Suggested KPI Rate: 15%. This response rate is a reasonable target for an Eol response rate. It signifies that the call for Eols has effectively engaged a portion of potential beneficiaries, demonstrating their interest in participating in the project.

KPI 3: Networking and Partnership Formation

Networking and Partnership Formation can be assessed by tracking the number of new partnerships or consortia formed as a direct result of the project's efforts. This may involve measuring:

- **Number of New Partnerships/Consortia Formed:** This is a quantitative measure of the new partnerships or consortia that have been established among suppliers, stakeholders, or other relevant entities within the project.
- **Number of Collaborative Activities:** This can include joint projects, initiatives, workshops, or other collaborative efforts that arise as a result of the project's networking activities.
- **Feedback from Stakeholders:** Gathering feedback from stakeholders who have formed partnerships to understand the impact, success, and effectiveness of these collaborations.

Suggested KPI Rate: 10. Forming 10 new partnerships or consortia demonstrates significant success in fostering collaboration and networking among stakeholders and suppliers.

5.2 Monitoring Mechanisms

Monitoring is a continuous process in PROCEDIN, ensuring that stakeholder engagement activities align with project goals and adapt to changing needs. **Surveys and feedback loops** are indispensable components of PROCEDIN's stakeholder engagement strategy, offering a systematic approach to gather insights, assess satisfaction, and make informed adjustments.

The project will regularly **design and administer surveys** that encompass a range of topics, including satisfaction with engagement activities, the relevance of project information, expectations, and suggestions for improvement.

On the other hand, **feedback loops** go beyond standard survey methodologies, as they involve creating a continuous and iterative process of gathering and acting upon feedback. PROCEDIN will collect feedback through various channels, such as emails, dedicated online forms, and interactive sessions during project events.

To maximise the effectiveness of surveys and feedback loops, the project team will employ a **PDCA** (Plan-Do-Check-Act) analysis approach, to ensure its engagement strategies are continuously refined and improved, addressing stakeholder needs and maximising the impact of project activities.

6 Risk Management

6.1 Identification of Potential Risks

In the process of stakeholder engagement within the PROCEDIN project, a comprehensive risk assessment has been conducted to anticipate and mitigate potential challenges. Three key risks have been identified, each with its unique characteristics and potential impact on the project's success. These risks include:

- **Risk 1: Inadequate Stakeholder Interest and Participation (Medium/High):** Engaging civil society and sustainability stakeholders may pose a challenge due to their varied interests, priorities, and often decentralised nature. This risk pertains to the possibility of stakeholders not showing the expected level of interest and participation in project activities, which could hinder the achievement of engagement goals.
- **Risk 2: Mismatched Expectations and Fatigue (Medium/Medium):** This risk involves the potential misalignment of stakeholder expectations with the project's objectives and outcomes, which could lead to misunderstandings and conflicts.
- **Risk 3: Resistance to Change (Low/Medium):** This risk considers the resistance that stakeholders may exhibit when faced with new approaches and practices introduced by the project, potentially impeding the adoption of POI practices.

The following sections will delve into each risk in detail, mitigation strategies, and contingency plans to proactively address these challenges.

6.2 Mitigation Strategies

The mitigation strategies detailed in the following Table 9 are tailored to the unique characteristics of each risk, offering a roadmap for addressing and, where possible, preventing these challenges.

Table 9. Mitigation Measures for Identified Risks

Risk 1: Inadequate Stakeholder Interest and Participation

To mitigate the risk of difficulty accessing relevant and motivated civil society and sustainability stakeholders, PROCEDIN has and will employ several strategies. This includes conducting an in-depth **stakeholder analysis** to identify and comprehend the specific interests, needs, and priorities of these groups (see 2.3 and 4.1). This analysis serves as the foundation for the tailoring of engagement approaches, ensuring alignment with project objectives and their concerns. **Collaborative workshops** will be organised to facilitate direct interactions between the PROCEDIN team and these stakeholders, fostering rapport, clarifying project objectives, and encouraging active participation. Moreover, a range of diverse and **inclusive communication channels**, including social media, webinars, and newsletters, will be implemented to effectively disseminate project information and updates, accommodating the varied communication preferences of civil society and sustainability stakeholders. Furthermore, **customised engagement plans** are developed to address the unique concerns and expectations of these stakeholders, ensuring that their interests are not only acknowledged but also fully integrated into the project's activities.

Risk 2: Mismatched Expectations and Fatigue

Mitigating the risk of mismatched expectations involves a multifaceted approach. To address this challenge, PROCEDIN will prioritise **clear and open communication with stakeholders**, commencing from the project's inception. This will include providing explicit definitions of project objectives, scope, and anticipated outcomes, as well as regular updates to stakeholders regarding progress and any shifts in project direction. Additionally, **tailored stakeholder engagement plans** are formulated, outlining their respective roles, responsibilities, and expected contributions. These plans are strategically aligned with the project's overarching goals and the unique objectives of each stakeholder. Furthermore, a **robust feedback mechanism** will be instituted, affording stakeholders the opportunity to express their concerns and expectations. Regular solicitation of stakeholder input will enable the project team to make any necessary adjustments to the project strategy, ensuring it remains congruent with stakeholders' expectations throughout the project's lifecycle.

Risk 3: Resistance to Change

To manage the risk of resistance to change effectively, PROCEDIN will implement a holistic approach. This includes the consortium discussion on **change management plan** that encompasses strategies for addressing any potential resistance. This discussion will not only identify areas where resistance may emerge but will also outline **effective communication strategies** to address concerns and **provide training programmes** to support stakeholders in adapting to new practices. Furthermore, stakeholders will be actively engaged in the decision-making process concerning these changes. Meaning, their input and feedback will be actively sought and thoughtfully considered as the engagement evolves.

6.3 Contingency Plans

Within the stakeholder engagement framework of the PROCEDIN project, the development of contingency plans is a vital component aimed at proactively addressing potential challenges and risks. These contingency plans (Table 10) represent crafted solutions to ensure that, in the face of unforeseen events or issues, the project can continue to navigate its engagement activities successfully.

Table 10. Contingency Plans for Identified Risks

Risk 1: Inadequate Stakeholder Interest and Participation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Alternative Engagement Strategies: Explore alternative strategies for engagement, such as partnering with intermediary organisations or thought leaders who have established connections with these stakeholders. ▪ Extended the EoI Timeline: If necessary, extend the Expression of Interest timeline to accommodate prolonged engagement efforts. This will allow for a more patient and accommodating approach to stakeholder involvement. ▪ Resource Allocation: Allocate additional resources, both in terms of time and budget, to intensify efforts aimed at bridging the engagement gap with civil society and sustainability stakeholders.
Risk 2: Mismatched Expectations and Fatigue
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conflict Resolution: In case of significant misalignment of expectations, PROCEDIN will implement a conflict resolution process. This may involve mediation or negotiations to reach a common understanding and agreement on how to move forward. • Revised Stakeholder Engagement: Reassess the stakeholder engagement plans and make necessary adjustments to realign expectations. This may include revising roles, responsibilities, and objectives to better match the project's evolving context.
Risk 3: Resistance to Change
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptive Change Approach: In cases of persistent resistance, consortium partners will consider adopting an adaptive change approach. This means making changes gradually or in smaller increments to allow stakeholders more time to adapt and accept new practices. • Alternative Strategies: If resistance remains a significant barrier, partners will be prepared to explore alternative strategies that may achieve project objectives while minimising disruption. These strategies should be carefully assessed to ensure they align with the project's overall goals.

7 Stakeholder Engagement Timeline

The Figure 7 provides an overview of the key activities and their respective timelines in the stakeholder engagement plan, encompassing the EoI process and the support and capacity-building activities associated with it.

Figure 7. Stakeholder Engagement Timeline

8 Conclusion

The Stakeholder Engagement Plan for the PROCEDIN project serves as a dynamic and multifaceted framework designed to foster meaningful and productive interactions with diverse stakeholder groups. Throughout the development of this plan, project partners have outlined a **comprehensive strategy that aligns with the project's goals and objectives**, placing stakeholder interests, ethical considerations, and data protection at the forefront. By identifying and **categorising stakeholders into distinct clusters**, we have set the stage for tailored engagement approaches that recognise the unique needs and expectations of each group.

The central goal of our engagement strategy is twofold: to **enhance existing networks and communities of practice** while also **extending our reach to new stakeholders**. This objective resonates through each facet of our plan, from the Call for Expression of Interest (EoI) to the support and capacity-building activities that underpin it. Through the EoI, we aim to connect with innovation buyers and providers, multipliers, and initiatives linked to procurement of innovation. This initiative will not only **broaden our stakeholder base** but also **facilitate partnerships and consortia formation among suppliers**.

This engagement plan is a living document, and in summarising this plan, we see a roadmap for productive engagement that emphasises stakeholder needs, fosters collaboration, and **drives the PROCEDIN project towards its overarching goals**. As we proceed, we will continually evaluate, adapt, and optimise our engagement strategies to ensure they remain responsive to changing stakeholder needs and project circumstances.